

The Transmutations of Time: A Retrospective Exhibition on Yang Zhichao's Performance Art

display

For over three decades now, Yang Zhichao has been researching an equilibrium across the three dimensions of Performance Art—the body, the site, and time. In Yang’s art, the site asks questions on who we are: Do I belong here? Am I sane? How do we get to understand one another in society? The body asks questions on control: Whose body is this? Do I have the freedom to break arbitrary boundaries between life and art? How do pain and violence that I do not control become a gateway to the most elusive and quotidian thoughts?

This exhibition focuses on the dimension of time in Yang Zhichao’s performance art, and particularly on the ways in which time turns into something else when a meditative connection between body and site is established. The body then becomes a vessel for the memory of what is meant to be forgotten—a tool to leave and receive traces of growth, alteration, loss, and dislocation. Recording the occurrence of simple events

also becomes a method for the sublimation and deposition of the substance of time. Hence, diaries, charts, and other methods of recording are important to Yang both as physical artifacts and as mnemonic tools to overcome the limits of the body and the site.

The works of performance art that Yang Zhichao has created in his long artistic career are numerous and varied, and this retrospective exhibition does not aim at presenting an exhaustive or even representative selection of them. Instead, by showing a very small and focussed set of his most meaningful works, it aims to introduce the viewer to Yang’s distinctively subdued and anti-spectacular approach to time-based art.

Yang Zhichao was born in 1963 in Yumen (Gansu Province, China), a city near the Gobi Desert known for its oil fields. He later went to school in nearby Jiayuguan, the site of the most westward fortress of

the Great Wall. While a university student in the provincial capital of Lanzhou, Yang begun practicing Performance Art both as a solo artist and as a founding member of the Lanzhou Art Army—one of the most important among the several groups of young and irreverent avant-garde artists that formed during the 1980s across China. His early art was influenced by European Surrealism and Joseph Beuys, and showed Yang’s admiration for the work of Taiwanese-American artist Tehching Hsieh. In 1998 Yang moved to Beijing to join its vibrant underground art scene. At the time, many artists were leaving their state-assigned jobs in the provinces to make experimental art in Beijing, despite the precarious living conditions. In Beijing Yang also met local artist and curator Ai Weiwei, who would assist him in the realization of some of his performances. In 2006 Yang settled with his family in Songzhuang, on the outskirts of Beijing, and continues to live there.

Performance existed before the invention of speaking and writing. That’s why it’s actually easy to understand performance art. Start by thinking more about the lived reality under your feet and there it is.

— art critic and curator Li Xianting

Professional Nanny
Performance. From 1 August 1995 until 1 August 1996. Lanzhou.

Rules:

1. Keep a daily record of the child’s diet, sleep, health and activities, of any purchases, and anything else concerning the concrete situation, one card a day, for a total of 365 cards. The front side of the card bears the footprint of the child.
2. Comply with the work and rest schedule and what is specified on the card.
3. During the execution of the performance, the nanny is not allowed to participate in any activity unrelated to a nanny’s behaviour.
4. Arrange ten special activities for the child during the execution period.
5. Do not interrupt the performance at will.

Execution: The artist took care of every need of his one-year-old child for one year.

Lightbox 1: Front of a daily card: “Professional Nanny: Performance Art Execution Card. Time: 1995.8.1–1996.8.1. Place: Lanzhou, China. Executed by: ”

Images on the panel: (1) Back of a daily card: “Professional Nanny: Daily Schedule”; (2) The artist in Lanzhou with his child. The t-shirt read, on the front: “Professional Nanny”. On the back (not shown here), it read: “Professional Nanny. Lanzhou, China. 1995.8.1–1996.8.1”

Jiayu Pass
Performance. From 30 December 1999 until 30 January 2000. Jiayuguan Psychiatric Hospital.

Rules:

1. Be admitted to a psychiatric hospital as a patient.
2. Accept the course of treatment arranged by the hospital.
3. Comply with the hospital’s system of rules.
4. Do not leave the hospital or discontinue the treatment without reason.

Execution: The artist was admitted to the psychiatric hospital in the

city of Jiayuguan (Jiayu Pass) with the help of family members. He was diagnosed with schizophrenia and spent one month in the hospital, where he was given medications, psychological support and other treatments. The performance was recorded with photos, videos, and a diary.

Lightbox 2: The artist in the toilets of the hospital.
Images on the panel: (1) The artist in the main ward of the hospital. (2) The artist’s diary of the performance.

Bodhi
Performance. 21 August 2011. Beijing and Asolo.

The artist wore Buddhist prayer beads around his neck while silently reciting the mantra *om mani padme hum*, which represents the innermost heart of Avalokiteśvara, the bodhisattva of compassion. In Buddhism, the Sanskrit term “bodhi” refers to awakening. The artist recited the mantra while exposing his upper body to the sun until it left marks of the fifty-five beads on his skin. The process lasted four hours. The performance took place in Beijing and was broadcast in real time to the Asolo Film Festival in Italy.

Lightbox 3 and image on the panel: photographs from the performance.

Book of Revelations No. 4: Hundred Days of 12 May
Performance. 19 August 2008. Muyu.

The artist and his wife Zhang Lan travelled to the town of Muyu town, in the county of Qingchuan, Sichuan province, a hundred days after the Wenchuan earthquake of 12 May 2008. This county was one of the worst hit by that earthquake and its over 5,000 aftershocks, which devastated northern Sichuan and killed 4,597 people in this county alone. Over 90,000 people died or went missing due to the earthquake.

In Chinese funerary culture, after mourning the death of a loved

one for a hundred days, the family would perform sacrificial rituals for the deceased, making offerings of flowers, food and wine. Sometimes Buddhist monks would be invited to chant scriptures. The ritual is simply referred to as “Hundred Days”.

On the site of a school building and dormitory that had collapsed into ruins during the quake, the couple carried out this performance artwork—part of a series entitled Book of Revelations—by inserting into the artist’s abdomen a fragment of pencil lead that they found on the ground. The operation was carried out by Zhang Lan.

Right after the operation, the police intervened and took both into custody for questioning.

The performance references the collapse of many shoddily built schoolhouses and dormitories during the earthquake and the consequent death of thousands of young students. For a long time after the earthquake, the authorities tried to suppress information on the number of school children who had died in the earthquake and citizens’ enquiries about the causes.

The performance lasted sixteen hours and was recorded with photographs and a detailed diary.

Images on the panel: photographs from the performance and a drawing of the performance plan.

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